

Additional information 1: Overview of the feeding characteristics measured during the EPG analysis.

variable	Old leaf	Young leaf	
Total duration non probing	45.6 ± 7.3	54.2 ± 5.5	ns
Total duration epidermis/mesophyll	152.2 ± 15.1	160.0 ± 12.6	ns
Mean duration epidermis/mesophyll	6.0 ± 1.0	6.6 ± 0.6	*
Number of ultra short probes <0.5 min	5.2 ± 1.0	9.9 ± 1.3	**
Number of short probes <3 min	19.2 ± 2.0	17.0 ± 1.7	ns
Total duration difficulties	85.0 ± 17.2	101.2 ± 16.5	ns
Number of difficulties	2.4 ± 0.6	2.0 ± 0.4	ns
Latency to 1st salivation	164.2 ± 22.0	212.4 ± 20.2	*
Total duration salivation	14.9 ± 3.3	19.3 ± 5.1	ns
Number of salivations	2.9 ± 0.4	2.8 ± 0.4	ns
Mean duration salivation	4.5 ± 1.1	6.2 ± 2.0	ns
% Salivation in phloem phase	6.1 ± 1.3	9.2 ± 2.3	ns
Latency to 1st phloem feeding	164.8 ± 22.1	213.1 ± 20.2	*
Latency to 1st sustained phloem feeding	154.7 ± 20.1	213.7 ± 20.1	*
Total duration phloem feeding	221.0 ± 19.5	184.2 ± 14.4	ns
Total duration sustained feeding	226.6 ± 18.7	181.7 ± 14.6	ns
Number of phloem feedings	2.4 ± 0.3	2.3 ± 0.3	ns
Number of sustained feedings	1.9 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.2	ns
Mean duration phloem feeding	119.2 ± 18.3	93.9 ± 10.8	ns
Mean duration sustained feeding	226.6 ± 18.7	181.7 ± 14.6	ns
Total duration xylem ingestion	36.6 ± 4.7	44.1 ± 15.8	ns
Number of xylem ingestions	0.8 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.4	ns

Duration times are shown in minutes. Mean ± SE. Mann-Whitney U pairwise comparisons were performed between young and old leaves, separately (*P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.0001, and ns = not significant). “Difficulties” involve penetration difficulties. “Sustained” involves events > 10 min. Latency was measured from the start of the recording. 29 and 34 biological replicates were recorded for old and young leaves, respectively.

Additional information 2: An overview of the fungicides and insecticides detected on the seeds.

Line 1

Comments: hym+vib+tef

Component	Result	Unit	Comments	Method of analysis
Hymexazool	12.3	g.a.i._unit		
Tefluthrin	9.1	g.a.i._unit		
Sedaxane	0.32	g.a.i._unit		
Fludioxonyl	0.60	g.a.i._unit		
Metalaxyl-M	0.51	g.a.i._unit		

Line 2

Comments: hym+vib+tef

Component	Result	Unit	Comments	Method of analysis
Hymexazool	11.4	g.a.i._unit		
Tefluthrin	6.5	g.a.i._unit		
Sedaxane	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Fludioxonyl	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Metalaxyl-M	<0.10	g.a.i._unit		

Line 3

Comments: hym+vib+tef

Component	Result	Unit	Comments	Method of analysis
Hymexazool	10.6	g.a.i._unit		
Tefluthrin	0.0	g.a.i._unit		
Sedaxane	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Fludioxonyl	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Metalaxyl-M	0.00	g.a.i._unit		

Line 4

Comments: hym+vib+tef

Component	Result	Unit	Comments	Method of analysis
Hymexazool	7.1	g.a.i._unit		
Tefluthrin	5.2	g.a.i._unit		
Sedaxane	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Fludioxonyl	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Metalaxyl-M	<0.10	g.a.i._unit		

Contact :

Phone: +31 6 15440907
Email: info.analyse@cosun.com

Report of analysis

Line 5

Comments: hym+vib+tef

Component	Result	Unit	Comments	Method of analysis
Hymexazool	10.8	g.a.i._unit		
Tefluthrin	8.7	g.a.i._unit		
Sedaxane	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Fludioxonyl	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Metalaxyl-M	0.00	g.a.i._unit		

Line 6

Comments: hym+vib+tef

Component	Result	Unit	Comments	Method of analysis
Hymexazool	11.2	g.a.i._unit		
Tefluthrin	8.5	g.a.i._unit		
Sedaxane	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Fludioxonyl	0.00	g.a.i._unit		
Metalaxyl-M	0.00	g.a.i._unit		

Additional information 3: Generalized linear model with a logit link function of the abundance of aphids with black deposits in relation to the age of the leaf and number of days of confinement on the plant.

Akaike Information Criterion is 216.36

	Estimate	se	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)/young leaf/confined for 3 days	-6.1837	0.5439	-11.370	< 2e-16	***
Old leaf	2.8347	0.3171	8.938	< 2e-16	***
Confined for 7 days	1.0580	0.5623	1.881	0.0599	ns
Confined for 10 days	3.4434	0.5072	6.789	1.13e-11	***
Confined for 14 days	5.0151	0.5164	9.711	< 2e-16	***

(*P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, and ns = not significant)

Additional information 4: Generalized linear mixed model with logit link function of the abundance of aphids with black deposits in relation to different sugar beet lines and number of days of confinement on the plant on data of the climate chamber experiment 1. The order is based on the lowest to highest probability to form black deposits. Akaike

Information Criterion is 296.6

	Estimate	se	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)/Line 2/confined for 7 days	-6.7485	0.8715	-7.743	9.70e-15	***
Line 5	0.5667	0.6184	0.916	0.35951	ns
Line 1	0.8016	0.6308	1.271	0.20378	ns
Line 6	0.9352	0.6208	1.506	0.13194	ns
Line 3	1.1216	0.6180	1.815	0.06953	ns
Line 4	2.0585	0.6269	3.284	0.00102	**
Confined for 10 days	3.9184	0.7479	5.239	1.61e-07	***
Confined for 14 days	7.2637	0.7738	9.387	< 2e-16	***

(*P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, and ns = not significant)

Additional information 5: Generalized linear mixed model with logit link function of the abundance of aphids with black deposits in relation to different sugar beet lines and number of days of confinement on the plant on data of the climate chamber experiment 2. Akaike Information Criterion is 258.8

	Estimate	se	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)/ Line 2/confined for 7 days	-5.8248	0.7007	-8.313	< 2e-16	***
Line 5	0.5714	0.5836	0.979	0.32750	ns
Line 1	1.0050	0.5830	1.724	0.08471	ns
Line 6	1.6259	0.6017	2.702	0.00689	**
Line 3	0.8305	0.5761	1.441	0.14946	ns
Line 4	1.5567	0.5720	2.721	0.00650	**
Confined for 10 days	2.1904	0.5429	4.034	5.48e-05	***
Confined for 14 days	4.6710	0.5276	8.853	< 2e-16	***

(*P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, and ns = not significant)

Additional information 6: Results of a generalized linear model with logit link function of the abundance of aphids with black deposits in relation to different sugar beet lines, moment of infection, and number of days of confinement on the plant on data of the field trial. Akaike Information Criterion is 2989.8

	Estimate	se	z value	Pr(> z)	
(Intercept)/Line 1/Infection /Confined for 4 days	-5.1791	0.4683	-11.060	< 2e-16	***
Line 2	2.1238	0.5618	3.780	0.000157	***
Line 3	1.9005	0.5592	3.399	0.000677	***
Line 4	1.9012	0.5613	3.387	0.000706	***
Line 5	2.5689	0.5582	4.602	4.19e-06	***
Line 6	1.5984	0.5653	2.828	0.004690	**
Infection 2 (May 25 th)	3.1478	0.4729	6.656	2.82e-11	***
Infection 3 (June 22 nd)	5.4251	0.4950	10.959	< 2e-16	***
Infection 4 (July 13 th)	3.4962	0.4848	7.212	5.50e-13	***
Confined for 8 days	2.0306	0.2599	7.812	5.64e-15	***
Line 2:Infection 2	-2.4415	0.5959	-4.097	4.18e-05	***
Line 3: Infection 2	-2.0300	0.5923	-3.427	0.000610	***
Line 4: Infection 2	-2.1128	0.5955	-3.548	0.000389	***
Line 5: Infection 2	-3.3217	0.6039	-5.500	3.79e-08	***
Line 6: Infection 2	-1.6595	0.5997	-2.767	0.005657	**
Line 2: Infection 3	-2.1508	0.6126	-3.511	0.000447	***
Line 3: Infection 3	-2.1162	0.6053	-3.496	0.000472	***
Line 4: Infection 3	-2.2130	0.6110	-3.622	0.000292	***
Line 5: Infection 3	-2.6052	0.6023	-4.326	1.52e-05	***
Line 6: Infection 3	-1.9597	0.6116	-4.204	0.001355	**
Line 2: Infection 4	-2.1649	0.6147	-3.522	0.000429	***
Line 3: Infection 4	-1.7746	0.6021	-2.948	0.003202	**
Line 4: Infection 4	-2.0858	0.6103	-3.418	0.000632	***

Line 5: Infection 4	-2.7944	0.6225	-4.489	7.16e-06	***
Line 6: Infection 4	-1.6139	0.6105	-2.643	0.008209	**
Line 2: Confined for 8 days	-0.6407	0.3594	-1.783	0.074652	ns
Line 3: Confined for 8 days	-0.3087	0.3520	-0.877	0.380479	ns
Line 4: Confined for 8 days	-0.7544	0.3572	-2.112	0.034709	*
Line 5: Confined for 8 days	-1.1332	0.3661	-3.095	0.001968	**
Line 6: Confined for 8 days	-0.7304	0.3521	-2.074	0.038055	*

(*P < 0.05, **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, and ns = not significant)